

DIRECTIONS OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS BY ASSESSING THE INVESTMENT CAPACITY OF THE REGIONS

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Abstract: *The article focuses on the econometric evaluation of the investment potential of the regions. Based on the research, scientific conclusions have been drawn up to attract investment and proposals have been developed.*

Keywords: *investment, potential of regions, investment attractiveness.*

Introduction

Ensuring stable and effective economic processes in the current conditions reflects the model of modern economic and social relations. In particular, among the financial factors of economic growth, we can note investment activity as the main indicator. In modern conditions, taking into account the investment potential, it is becoming important to create investment attractiveness. The research of the theoretical bases of investment attractiveness at the micro (region, enterprise) and macro (country) levels is considered to have its own characteristics. To ensure investment attractiveness and rational use of investment potential, attention should be paid to the following:

□ to support the formation of investment strategies for the deployment and development of production forces, which will allow the implementation of the model of effective management of investment processes in the regions;

□ achieving synergistic and multiplicative effect by strengthening the level of institutionalization in terms of economic purposefulness, inter-sectoral cooperation, and the addressability of investment objects aimed at increasing

investment attractiveness in order to stabilize the economic potential of the regions;

□ acceleration of investment activities aimed at the innovative renewal of the socio-economic system of the region, firstly, the emergence of regional research institutes, and secondly, increasing the level of diversification that ensures innovative orientation of investments;

□ implementation of investments on the basis of financing based on the principles of cross-sectoral interests;

□ development of a database based on multiple components aimed at ensuring the processes of activation of investment activity in the regions.

Analysis of literature on the topic

A group of Russian scientists conducted their research in this direction and formulated their scientific conclusions. For example, A.M. Margolin and A. Ya. Bystryakovs look at investment in terms of benefit and note that it is reflected as “any long-term capital investment for the purpose of obtaining economic or social benefits in the future”.[1]

According to A.Semina [2], foreign literature states that investments exist in the following form. In a broad sense, it reflects the allocation of capital investments for the use of long-term consumer goods or the acquisition of new assets. In a narrow sense, it implies the organization of the development of basic means in various sectors of the economy in order to obtain material benefits or to achieve efficiency.

According to L. Abalki [3], he emphasizes the quality of investment activity as a means of making long-term capital investments in enterprises of various sectors of the economy.

The guide published under the editorship of A. Vakhobov [4] describes the role of international financial institutions in the regulation of investments and their specific aspects.

In particular, special emphasis is placed on the principles that should be paid attention to when attracting foreign investments. I.F.D. Sh. Mustafakulov [5] notes that it is important to ensure the socio-economic stability of regions in the implementation of investment activities. In particular, by directing investments to the real sector of the economy, the following socio-economic effects will be achieved,

Therefore, the assessment of investment attractiveness depends on a number of factors, as well as on the investment policy. In order to solve the issue of attracting investments to the region, it is necessary to develop a regional investment policy. In short, regional investment policy is the activity of regional administration bodies, which should be aimed at finding the source of investments and directing them to areas of effective use.

Research methodology

In the implementation of the research, correlational-regression analysis methods were used between the gross regional products of the regions and investment trends based on panel data and the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Analysis and results

We use the investment potential category to assess investment attractiveness. At the same time, we use economic-mathematical methods to analyze the share in the creation of the gross regional product. We performed a regression analysis to analyze the share of investments in the region(s) of our country in creating the gross regional product. Data were selected for the period 2013-2017. Based on the conducted research, it can be said that in a number of regions, the share of investments in the creation of added value is not direct, but has an indirect character.

Continuing our research, we will consider the relationship between the volume of investment in fixed capital per capita in the regions and the gross

regional product. For this, we conduct research using the regression analysis methodology. In this regard, the level of population accumulation is also important. For example, J. Keynes notes that there is a tendency for people to change their consumption as their income increases [6].

Of course, the creation of the gross regional product takes into account the consumption of the population. Therefore, the volume of investments per capita is of particular importance in shaping regional economic growth. Based on the conducted research, it can be noted that the volume of investments in fixed capital per capita in the regions of Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Namangan, Surkhandarya, Syrdarya and Tashkent city shows that it is becoming important in the creation of added value.

In our opinion, high investment per capita is not an important factor in creating added value. The important point here is to avoid sudden changes in per capita investment over the years. It is important to monitor this situation and take it into account when developing forecast indicators.

Table 1

Regression analysis of foreign investment (loans) included in fixed capital in the regions and trends of GNP development

The name of the areas	Coefficients		P-value		F-value
	Free limit	A free variable	Free limit	A free variable	
Karakalpakstan Republic	6412,0	-0,82	0,04	0,52	0,52
Andijan region	546,8	73,5	0,91	0,14	3,84
Bukhara region	7974,8	0,51	0,00	0,15	3,5
Jizzakh region	2108,2	26,8	0,05	0,04	11,3
Kashkadarya	5710,0	5,3	0,07	0,03	13,6

region					
Navoi region	8982,1	0,8	0,03	0,93	0,00
Namangan region	4540,4	5,8	0,00	0,00	103,9
Samarkand region	-1118,5	208,6	0,42	0,18	2,98
Surkhandarya region	1323,2	29,1	0,37	0,00	43,0
Syrdarya region	4818,2	-14,3	0,29	0,74	0,12
Tashkent region	3938,0	23,6	0,43	0,05	9,9
Fergana region	23786,5	-55,3	0,19	0,46	0,69
Khorezm region	3913,3	19,4	0,07	0,22	2,27
Tashkent city	10839,2	13,1	0,08	0,02	17,1

When thinking about the investment potential of the regions, the influence of attracted foreign investments on the process of creating added value is important. The reason is that the attracted foreign funds should be reflected in the economic growth of the region based on its capacity.

It can be noted that the economic growth in Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Namangan regions and the city of Tashkent depends on foreign funds. In these areas, it can be seen that each foreign investment in Namagan and Kashkadarya regions has a synergistic effect of 5 units in the creation of gross regional product.

Conclusions and suggestions

In our opinion, in order to ensure a positive correlation between investments in fixed capital and gross regional products, we believe that it is appropriate to pay attention to the following:

□ to ensure a stable share of investments attracted to the region in relation to the gross regional product;

□ to prevent sharp changes in investment trends compared to the previous year;

□ to ensure that investments have a positive role in the creation of gross regional product, to focus on ensuring that the share of investment volume in relation to gross product is according to international standards (25-40 percent).

In our opinion, the creation of gross regional product in Kashkadarya, Namangan regions and Tashkent city has a tendency to develop in harmony with the growth of local and foreign investments. It should be noted that the investments attracted in these regions are not of consumption nature, but of value creation nature. It is known from the conducted research that although the development trends of local investments in the Jizzakh region have an indirect effect on the creation of added value, the share of foreign funds in the creation of the gross product reflects a direct relationship.

We would like to point out that among the regions with a positive investment potential, we can mention Bukhara, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Navoi, Namangan, Surkhandarya, Syrdarya regions and the city of Tashkent. Therefore, it can be said that investment activity is provided based on the existing potential in the mentioned regions. In our opinion, it is appropriate to pay attention to the following cases when attracting foreign investments to the regions:

□ placement of investments taking into account natural and climatic conditions;

□ implementation of investment projects, taking into account the level of specialization;

□ placement of investments in priority areas, taking into account opportunities for competitive advantage;

□ taking into account its positive impact on economic growth rather than the volume of investments.

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